

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

D3.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment

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R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment

Researchers organise lectures, seminars, or workshops connected to every secondment, typically one at host institution during secondment, one at home institution after reintegration.

Secondments and their accompanying deliverables take place within Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society or Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. At the onset of the secondment, in the Researcher Declaration Form, researchers indicate whether their research topic falls within WP2 or WP3. The following list contains lectures, seminars, or workshops that PRODIGEES researchers organised at their host institution and host institution within the theme of WP3. Presentations not included in the list are those related to PRODIGEES Network-Wide events: MGG PRODIGEES Authors Workshop (2022), MGG PRODIGEES Policy Labs (2024), MGG PRODIGEES Final Conference (2025), and the yearly Transnational Open Access Trainings (2020-2025). Secondment Activity Reports were to be submitted within 30 days after the end of the respective secondment; therefore, not all presentations at the home institution after the secondment have yet taken place.

- Bilotta, N. (2022, August 26). Can digital currencies end financial exclusion in Indonesia? Economic realities and policy ambitions.
- Bilotta, N. (2022, December 6). Can digital currencies end financial exclusion in Indonesia? Webinar with Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI), Rome, Italy.
- Bilotta, N., Dries, J., Fauri, A. (2025, March 11). Central Banks' Digital Currencies (CBDC).
- Colantoni, L. (2023, December 17). Amazon Immersion Experience.
- Colantoni, L. (2023, November 6). Technologies to fight global deforestation: the case of Indonesia.
- Colantoni, L. (2023, October 23). The EUDR and forest protection at the crossroads
- Crossa, M. (2025, February 19). Industry 4.0 in the automotive production chains: A Global Phenomenon? Return presentation at Istituto Mora
- Crossa, M. (2024, December 17). Industry 4.0 in the automotive production chains: A Global Phenomenon?
- Daulay, N., Fauri, A., Krisetya, B., Rachman, R., Widiyati, V. A. (2025, March 6): Joint presentation of PRODIGEES secondment research findings at CSIS
- Fauri, A. (2023, December 12). Navigating the needs of CBDC: Exploring the objective and design of CBDC in the Indonesian context.
- Giordano, A. (2024, September 18). Digitisation and Geographical Technologies for Sustainability: A Comparative Analysis of OECM Advancements in Mexico and Italy.
- Giri, T. (2023, November 28). Navigating Sustainable Procurement in Brazil's ENAP
- Giri, T., Rafitrandi, D. (2025, March 11). Trends in the Digital Economy.
- Hernandez, A. M. (2022, December 14). Impressions from the field research on the potential role of digitalization in curbing food waste and loss (FWL).
- Hernandez, A. M. (2022, May 17). State of the art on sustainability standards in various sectors in Brazil.
- Hernandez, A. M. (2022, May 4). Workshop at the National Institute of Metrology, Standardization and Industrial Quality (INMETRO), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.
- Jauregui Fung, F. G. (2025, January 23.) Co-benefits of the integration of mass-transit systems. Lessons from Jakarta.
- Jauregui Fung, F. G. (2024, November 5). Co-benefits of mass transit for land value uplift and transit-oriented development in emerging economies: Lessons from Jakarta
- Lucatello, S. (2020, December 20). CIFE Webinar: Digitalisation and Climate Change I.
- Lucatello, S. (2021, January 21). CIFE Webinar: Digitalisation and Climate Change II.
- Lucatello, S. (2022, December 7). Digitalisation and Sustainability.
- Mansur, J. A. (2023, August 02). Women in Entrepreneurship: Examining the Role of Female Leadership in Fostering Sustainable Development Practices

Mansur, J. A. (2023, July 13). Female entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector: Brazil and Germany.

Miozza, M. (2023, February 08). Research Projects Presentation. Research Information System for Developing Countries (RIS).

Oliveira, R. S. (2023, November 23). Upscaling the macroeconomic modeling for climate adaptation.

Polito, C. (2024, March 13). Biometric technologies: An Unstable network. Unveiling the Dynamics of E-Gate Implementation at Cape Town International Airport

Rafitrandi, D. (2022, October 31). The EU and Indonesia economic cooperation in the twin transition.

Sangiorgio, A. (2025, March 13). Satellites & Environmental Monitoring in India. Workshop with Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI)

Sarno, G. S. (2022, December 20). Urban resilience to extreme natural events and climate change: from Brasil to Europe. Workshop with FGV, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Sarno, G. S. (2022, September 6). Waterproofing data.

Sosa Núñez, Gustavo (2020, October 5). Use of artificial intelligence in climate change mitigation and adaptation policies: A comparative study between the EU, Germany and Mexico.

Widiyadi, A. (2025, January 30). Digitalisation and Climate Transparency Mechanisms.

